

Citation for the Presentation of the
2014 ICPE Medal to

Professor Cedric Linder

Department of Physics and Astronomy
Uppsala University, Sweden

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Cedric Linder is Professor of Physics Education Research in the Department of Physics and Astronomy at Uppsala University in Sweden. He is awarded the ICPE Medal for 2014 in recognition of his outstanding contributions to physics education research. His work has been notable for its range, depth, consistency and impact, as well for its international scope.

In 1979 Cedric Linder graduated with Honours in Physics and Electronics from Rhodes University in South Africa. After completing a teaching diploma, he became a high school teacher of mathematics and science in Cape Town. The award of a Fulbright Scholarship in 1980 took him to Rutgers University in the USA, where he obtained a Master's degree in Science Education. Following his return to Cape Town he became a Lecturer in the Physics Department at the University of the Western Cape. Another excursion, this time to Canada, led to a doctorate in Science Education from the University of British Columbia in 1989. His thesis work looked at learning challenges faced by physics graduate students in the area of sound. Returning to the University of the Western Cape, Cedric Linder set up a highly successful physics education group. This led to him being promoted to the first personal chair in Physics Education in South Africa in 1996, and he went on to serve as Chairperson of the Physics Department. In 2000 he moved to his current position at Uppsala University, becoming the first Professor of Physics Education Research in Sweden. Cedric Linder retains his professorship at the University of the Western Cape and is also a guest professor at Linnaeus University in Kalmar, Sweden.

Cedric Linder has been a pioneer and innovator throughout his career. He has shown leadership in many areas of teaching and research, including the introduction of conceptual physics as an integral component of service and mainstream physics education, the development of subject-based educational research, and the scholarship of teaching and learning. Three of his achievements deserve special mention. First, his success in changing the way that physics is taught by using novel techniques to enable colleagues to appreciate the students' experience of learning physics. Second, the opening up of physics for disadvantaged students with life-enhancing and life-changing effects. Third, the addition of new theoretical insights and methodological approaches to the practice of physics education research.

Cedric Linder's education was the result of studies undertaken in several countries.

It is therefore fitting that students in many lands should now be benefitting from the work of a teacher and educational researcher that international education has produced.

Today the International Commission on Physics Education takes great pleasure in recognizing that researcher, and the significance of his work, by awarding him the 2014 ICPE Medal for outstanding contributions to international physics education.

August 2014
Robert Lambourne
Chairman of ICPE